

THE NEED FOR A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO THE FORMATION OF FINANCIAL POLICY IN ENTERPRISES

Khamdamov Sardor Farmon ugli

TSEU independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10429999>

Abstract. The main characteristic of financial relations is that they have a distributive nature, and accordingly the main or main function of finance is distribution. The process of distribution, which must be carried out with the help of finance, is a complex and multifaceted process. Of course, important factors in the achievement of economic and financial stability of our country are the growth of production volume, reduction of currency depreciation, increase of export volume and other similar macro-economic growth, as well as ensuring the economic growth of every enterprise, firm, and company operating in our republic. It requires development as a social entity.

Keywords: Enterprise activity, foreign investments, modern marketing, financial relations, bank credit, leasing operations, economic entities, economic indicators.

INTRODUCTION

The main characteristic of financial relations is that they have a distributive nature, and accordingly the main or main function of finance is distribution. The process of distribution, which must be carried out with the help of finance, is a complex and multifaceted process. Finance serves different stages of GDP distribution, participates in its primary distribution and redistribution.

Distribution through the financial method covers different levels of economic management (at the level of the country, its separate regions and local self-government bodies). It is characterized by multi-levels that give rise to different forms of distribution (intra-farm, intra-network, inter-branch, inter-regional, etc.).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The whole system of financial management is based on the financial policy of the state. That is why financial policy is the most basic element in the financial management system. Financial policy is the independent activity of the state in the field of financial relations. This activity is aimed at providing appropriate financial resources for the implementation of one or another economic and social development program of the state.

Financial policy has a self-sustaining independent importance, and at the same time it is an important means of implementing state policy in any sphere of

social activity. Here, it is not of principle importance whether it is the economy, social sphere, military reforms or international relations.

Politics, political influence and political leadership consist of the following three elements:

to define and set the main goal and to specify the tasks in the future and in the near future that need to be solved in order to achieve the set goals specific to a certain period of society's life; development of methods, tools and concrete forms of relations that will achieve the set goals in a short period of time, and the tasks of the near days and in the future will be solved in a reasonable order; selection and placement of personnel capable of solving assigned tasks, organizing their implementation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The state financial policy should be considered as a part of the state socio-economic policy to ensure the growth of financial resources in a balanced (proportioned) manner at all levels of the country's financial system. Foreign experience shows that denying the need for a balanced growth of financial resources leads to the degradation of the country's financial system itself, the collapse and destruction of the economy.

The main characteristic of the financial policy is that this policy should be directed to the development of the country's productive forces and to have a continuous impact on economic success.

The purpose of the company's financial policy can be [2]:

- achieving a healthy life (performance) of the enterprise in the conditions of competition;
- avoid major financial failures and bankruptcy;
- to achieve leadership (to be a leader) in the struggle with competitors; maximizing the market value of the enterprise;
- sustainable growth of the economic potential of the enterprise; increase the volume of production and sales;
- profit maximization; cost minimization; ensuring profitable activity and others.

Management (English "management" - to manage, manage, organize) is [4]:

- practical activities aimed at certain goals in the management of production and commerce;
- management theory science is a set of management principles, methods, tools and forms;

— is the leading structure of the enterprise, joint-stock company in the current practice of our country.

The management process is a set of continuous, consistent, interconnected actions on the formation and use of the organization's resources to achieve its goals. These actions are called management tasks. Thus, the management process is the total sum of all tasks. Management tasks are relatively independent, specialized and separated types of management activities. The management function of such a calculation should have a clearly reflected content, a developed mechanism for its implementation, and a certain structure within which its organizational separation is completed. The content is understood as an action that must be carried out within the framework of a specific task. The content of the actions and tasks performed in the management process depends on the type of organization (administrative, social, educational, etc.), the scope of its activities and areas (production, trade, providing services), level in the management hierarchy (upper, middle or lower level of management), role within the organization (production, marketing, finance, personnel) and a number of other factors. there will be the same types of activities. According to A. Fayol, who was the first to develop this concept in 1916, there are five primary tasks: management means predicting and planning, organizing, directing, coordinating and controlling. We are talking about tasks that are components of any process of management, regardless of the characteristics of this or that organization (size, designation, forms of ownership, etc.), therefore they are called general. Modern researchers have developed another list of management functions: planning, organizing, directing (or giving orders), motivating, leading, coordinating, controlling, communicating, researching, evaluating, making decisions, selecting employees, representing and negotiating, and making deals. In practice, in every case of management, general management tasks are slightly different from management. Nevertheless, we consider it appropriate to distinguish five general tasks of management [5]:

- planning (choosing goals and action plan to achieve them);
- organization (distribution of tasks between departments or employees and establishment of mutual cooperation between them);
- motivation (encouraging performers to implement planned actions and achieve set goals);
- coordination (ensures compatibility and compatibility between various parts of the managed system by establishing reasonable connections);

— control (comparison of actual achievable or achieved results with planned ones).

CONCLUSION

Today, our republic has a comprehensive scientific program aimed at mechanizing agriculture, applying modern techniques and technologies that provide for the effective use of modern science and technology, and improving the existing ones to increase the productivity of agricultural products obtained from crops. and innovative works are being carried out.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2016 No. PF-4861 "On measures to ensure rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
2. Vakhobov A., Malikov —T.: - T.: Economy - finance. 2018.
3. Vahobov A., Ibrohimov A., Ishankulov N. Financial and management analysis. Textbook. — T.: "Sharq" 2015
4. B.B Kovalev, O.H. Volkova. Analysis of the economic activity of an enterprise: Textbook. - M: TK Welby, "Prospect", 2014.- 424 p.
5. Vasileva M.V., Maliy N.A. Financial policy - Rostov N/A Phoenix. 2018.
6. Galitskaya S.V. Financial management. -M.: Eksmo, 2019.
7. Galitskaya S.V. The financial analysis. -M.: Eksmo, 2019.

